

Halogenation. Part XVI. Bromination and Iodination of Mesitylene.

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The present paper describes the bromination of mesitylene in presence of fuming nitric acid and the iodination of mesitylene in presence of nitro-sulphonic acid mixture. The substances obtained are the mono-, di- and tri-bromo- and mono-, di- and tri-iodo derivatives of mesitylene. These were identified with the products obtained by the previous workers by other methods (Fittig and Storer, *Annalen*, 1868, 147, 6; Schram, *Ber.*, 1886, 19, 212; Tohl, *Ber.*, 1892, 25, 1522; Tohl and Eichel, *Ber.*, 1893, 26, 1100.)

Iodination of 2-bromomesitylene in presence of nitrosulphonic acid mixture yields the hitherto undescribed 2-bromo-4-iodomesitylene.

EXPERIMENTAL.

2-Bromomesitylene.—To mesitylene (10 c.c.) in a flask, bromine (3.5 c.c.) was added drop by drop in about 30 minutes. Fuming nitric acid (3.5 c.c.) was then added to it in the cold slowly and the mixture allowed to stand for about 2 hours. The product was washed free of bromine by 2% sodium hydroxide solution, dried and distilled. The unused mesitylene distilled over first and then the mono-bromomesitylene (7.5 c.c.) at about 224°. When the same experiment was repeated either on a water-bath or on a sand-bath the resulting compound was very much contaminated with the nitro-derivatives.

2:4-Dibromomesitylene.—To mesitylene (5 c.c.) and acetic acid (5 c.c.), bromine (3.5 c.c.) was added with shaking. Fuming nitric acid (2 c.c.) was then added and allowed to stand for about 2 hours. The product was extracted with carbon tetrachloride, washed free of bromine, dried and allowed to crystallise. Needle-shaped crystals (5.6 g.), m.p. 62°.

2:4:6-Tribromomesitylene.—The previous experiment was repeated using 5.2 c.c. of bromine and 1 c.c. of fuming nitric acid and the product worked up as before. It (8.0 g.) melted at 222°.

2:4-Diiodomesitylene.—Mesitylene (5 c.c.), iodine (5.5 g.) and glacial acetic acid (5 c.c.) were taken in a flask and refluxed on a water bath. Nitrosulphonic acid mixture (3 c.c.) was added drop by drop and heated for 3 hours. The product was extracted with benzene, washed free of iodine, dried and the benzene and the unused mesitylene distilled over. The residue in the distilling flask was crystallised from rectified spirit as white needles (4.5 g.), m.p. 82°-83°.

2:4:6-Tri-iodomesitylene has been obtained from *2:4-diiodomesitylene* (4 g.), iodine (5 g.), acetic acid (10 c.c.) and nitrosulphonic acid (5 c.c.) by the preceding method. White flaky crystals (6.5 g.), m.p. 208°.

2-Bromo-4-iodomesitylene.—*2-Bromomesitylene* (5 c.c.) was iodinated as mentioned above with iodine (5 g.), acetic acid (15 c.c.) and nitrosulphonic acid mixture (5 c.c.) on a sand-bath for about an hour and a half. On cooling, a shining white solid mass separated out. It was removed from the rest of the liquid and extracted with benzene. The benzene extract was washed free of iodine by shaking with 5% solution of sodium hydroxide and then with water, dried over fused calcium chloride and the excess of benzene distilled off. On allowing the solution to cool, white needle-shaped crystals (4 g.) separated out. On crystallisation from benzene it melted at 175-76°. It is soluble in alcohol and benzene. (Found: Total halogen, 64.10. $C_9H_{10}BrI$ requires Total halogen, 63.68 per cent).

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